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Feral pigeons as reservoirs of zoonotic pathogens in the urban environment: Spatial clustering and molecular evidence

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Abstract:	<p>Feral pigeons (<i>Columba livia</i> f. <i>domestica</i>) are common inhabitants of cities and often come into close contact with humans. This study aimed to investigate the prevalence and spatial distribution of zoonotic pathogens in feral pigeons, with emphasis on <i>Chlamydia psittaci</i>, <i>Mycobacterium avium</i> complex and <i>Salmonella enterica</i>. Given its emergence in passerine birds, <i>Trichomonas gallinae</i> was included, although it is not considered a zoonotic species. A total of 175 pooled faecal samples representing 875 individual droppings were collected from 35 localities across three urban zones. Two multiplex real-time PCR (qPCR) assays were developed and validated to detect the presence of target organisms. Spatial clustering of positive findings was analysed using hierarchical clustering based on geographic distances.</p> <p><i>C. psittaci</i> was the most prevalent pathogen, found in 20.6% of faecal samples. <i>T. gallinae</i> was detected in 9.7%, <i>S. enterica</i> in 4.0%, and <i>M. avium</i> subsp. <i>hominissuis</i> in 1.1%. <i>M. avium</i> subsp. <i>avium</i> was not detected. Based on average pairwise geographic distances, statistically significant spatial clustering of <i>C. psittaci</i>-positive flock was shown, suggesting non-random distribution of infection. The study highlights urban feral pigeons as potential carriers of zoonotic pathogens, particularly <i>C. psittaci</i>, which shows spatial clustering in densely populated urban areas. The results support the need for monitoring potential zoonotic risks associated with urban pigeon excretions to human health. These findings provide essential baseline data for public health authorities and contribute to risk assessment and urban wildlife management strategies in Central European cities.</p>
Opposed Reviewers:	

Dear Editor,

I am pleased to submit our manuscript entitled “**Feral Pigeons as Reservoirs of Zoonotic Pathogens in the Urban Environment: Spatial Clustering and Molecular Evidence**” for consideration for publication in the *Veterinary Microbiology*.

Our study investigated the prevalence and spatial distribution of zoonotic pathogens in feral pigeons, with emphasis on *Chlamydia psittaci*, *Mycobacterium avium* complex and *Salmonella enterica*. *Trichomonas gallinae*, non-zoonotic protozoan, with high significance as emerging pathogen for passerines was included as well. Zoonotic *Chlamydia psittaci* was found in over 20% of faecal samples. *T. gallinae* was detected in 9.7 %, *S. enterica* in 4.0 %, and *M. avium* subsp. *hominissuis* in 1.1 %. *M. avium* subsp. *avium* was not detected. Statistically significant spatial clustering of *C. psittaci*-positive flock was shown, suggesting non-random distribution of infection within the city. These results support continued monitoring of zoonotic risks from urban pigeon excreta and provide baseline data for public-health and wildlife-management decisions in Central European cities.

Given the journal’s focus on microbial diseases of wild animals, including the members of feral fauna, we believe that our findings will be of great interest to the readers of the *Veterinary Microbiology*. The manuscript has not been published previously and is not under consideration elsewhere. All authors have approved the manuscript and agree with its submission.

We appreciate your time and consideration, and we look forward to the opportunity to contribute to your journal.

Sincerely,

Radka Dzedzinska

Highlights

- Urban pigeons can carry aetiological agents of zoonotic diseases
- Zoonotic *Chlamydia psittaci* was found in over 20% of pigeon droppings
- *T. gallinae*, re-emerging pathogen of passerines was proven in 9.7% of feral pigeons
- *C. psittaci*-positive flocks show clustering, non-random distribution in urban areas
- Pigeon monitoring supports local authorities in setting effective preventive measures

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2 **Feral pigeons as reservoirs of zoonotic pathogens in the urban environment: Spatial**
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4 **clustering and molecular evidence**
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1 **ABSTRACT**

2 Feral pigeons (*Columba livia f. domestica*) are common inhabitants of cities and often come
3 into close contact with humans. This study aimed to investigate the prevalence and spatial
4 distribution of zoonotic pathogens in feral pigeons, with emphasis on *Chlamydia psittaci*,
5 Mycobacterium avium complex and *Salmonella enterica*. Given its emergence in passerine
6 birds, *Trichomonas gallinae* was included, although it is not considered a zoonotic species. A
7 total of 175 pooled faecal samples representing 875 individual droppings were collected from
8 35 localities across three urban zones. Two multiplex real-time PCR (qPCR) assays were
9 developed and validated to detect the presence of target organisms. Spatial clustering of
10 positive findings was analysed using hierarchical clustering based on geographic distances.
11 *C. psittaci* was the most prevalent pathogen, found in 20.6 % of faecal samples. *T. gallinae*
12 was detected in 9.7 %, *S. enterica* in 4.0 %, and *M. avium* subsp. *hominissuis* in 1.1 %.
13 *M. avium* subsp. *avium* was not detected. Based on average pairwise geographic distances,
14 statistically significant spatial clustering of *C. psittaci*-positive flock was shown, suggesting
15 non-random distribution of infection. The study highlights urban feral pigeons as potential
16 carriers of zoonotic pathogens, particularly *C. psittaci*, which shows spatial clustering in
17 densely populated urban areas. The results support the need for monitoring potential zoonotic
18 risks associated with urban pigeon excretions to human health. These findings provide
19 essential baseline data for public health authorities and contribute to risk assessment and
20 urban wildlife management strategies in Central European cities.

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22 **Keywords:** pigeon; psittacosis; qPCR; clustering; public health; urban zoonoses

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26 1. Introduction

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28 Feral pigeon (*Columba livia f. domestica*), descendants of domesticated rock pigeon
29 (*Columba livia*), has become an integral part of many urban ecosystems, particularly since the
30 mid-20th century. Feral pigeons are characterised by wide ecological plasticity enabling them
31 to colonise a wide range of urban environments. The main limiting factor for feral pigeon
32 populations is the availability of suitable nesting sites. Pigeons inhabit densely built historical
33 centres, residential areas, industrial zones and peripheral green spaces. Their spatial
34 distribution within cities is also influenced by the availability of food resources and the degree
35 of human disturbance, resulting in considerable heterogeneity in population densities across
36 the urban landscape (Arizaga et al., 2023; Haagwackernagel, 1995; Hetmanski et al., 2011).
37 High densities are typically observed in central urban areas, particularly around public
38 squares, markets, and transport hubs, where food sources and nesting opportunities are
39 abundant (Arizaga et al., 2023; Hetmanski et al., 2011; Rose and Nagel, 2006). However,
40 urban pigeon populations may not rely solely on resources within the city, as birds frequently
41 forage in surrounding agricultural areas, especially after harvest or during periods of reduced
42 urban food availability (Rose and Nagel, 2006).

43 The presence of feral pigeons in urban areas is associated with several negative
44 impacts, particularly damage to buildings, neighbouring fields and potential health risks to
45 residents and other wild animals. Each pigeon produces approximately 12 kg of droppings
46 annually, contributing to significant urban maintenance costs (Haag-Wackernagel and
47 Geigenfeind, 2008). The acidic and chemically active nature of these excreta leads to the
48 degradation of stone, metal, and other building materials. Additionally, the nutrient deposits
49 promote microbial growth that further accelerates biodegradation (Spennemann et al., 2017).
50 These effects are exacerbated by the ingestion of human-derived, often acidic food waste,

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51 which alters the physicochemical properties of droppings and intensifies their corrosiveness
52 (Spennemann et al., 2017). This creates economic burdens for municipalities and reduces
53 urban aesthetic appeal.

54 The widespread occurrence and high population densities of feral pigeons in urban
55 areas increase the likelihood of human exposure to the birds themselves or their droppings.
56 Pigeon nests in lofts, terraces, or other parts of buildings can serve as reservoirs for
57 ectoparasites, including soft ticks (*Argas reflexus*) and other species such as *Ceratophyllus*
58 *columbae*, *Cimex columbarius*, and *Dermanyssus gallinae* (Bonney et al., 2008). These may
59 infest buildings, causing allergic reactions or, albeit rarely, direct attacks on humans (Haag-
60 Wackernagel and Bircher, 2010). In addition, feral pigeons are recognised reservoirs of
61 numerous zoonotic pathogens, including viruses, bacteria, fungi, and protozoa. Although only
62 a few viruses isolated from urban bird populations have been directly linked to human
63 infections, some fungi, notably *Cryptococcus neoformans*, have been associated with pigeon
64 droppings and subsequent human disease (Bonney et al., 2008). Due to their stable
65 abundance and spatial mobility between cities and surrounding rural areas, feral pigeons
66 represent a persistent and reliable reservoir of zoonotic agents in local ecosystems (Mia et al.,
67 2022).

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68 *Chlamydia psittaci*, the causative agent of psittacosis, has been epidemiologically
69 linked to human cases (Henry and Crossley, 1986) and was often detected in feral pigeons in
70 various cities in past (Geigenfeind et al., 2012; Kowalczyk and Wojcik-Fatla, 2022; Magnino
71 et al., 2009). Enteric bacteria such as *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter* spp., and *Escherichia*
72 *coli* are commonly isolated from pigeon populations (Mia et al., 2022; Perez-Sancho et al.,
73 2020). In the context of rising global antimicrobial resistance, the detection of multidrug-
74 resistant strains in urban pigeon populations represents an emerging concern for public health
75 (Radimersky et al., 2010). Pigeons have also been identified as carriers of tick-borne

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76 pathogens, including *Borrelia burgdorferi* sensu lato, *Bartonella* spp., *Rickettsia* spp., and
77 *Coxiella burnetii* (Ebani et al., 2016). A comprehensive overview of zoonotic microorganisms
78 associated with urban pigeon populations has been published by the World Health
79 Organization (Bonney et al., 2008).

80 This study aimed to assess the presence of selected zoonotic pathogens in feral pigeon
81 populations in Brno, the second-largest city in the Czech Republic (population ~400,000).
82 The investigation focused on *Chlamydia psittaci*, *Mycobacterium avium* complex (including
83 *M. avium* subsp. *avium*, the causative agent of avian tuberculosis), and *Salmonella enterica*
84 subsp. *enterica*., using real-time PCR (qPCR). The protozoan *Trichomonas gallinae*, non-
85 zoonotic, but a re-emerging pathogen implicated in recent epizootics among European
86 passerines, was also included. This work forms part of a broader research initiative addressing
87 the risks of zoonotic disease transmission linked to increasing interactions between wildlife
88 and urban environments. The study was initiated in collaboration with local public authorities,
89 who required epidemiological data for urban bird management strategies and public health
90 risk assessments.

91 92 **2. Material and Methods**

93 *2.1. Sample collection*

94 The study was designed to minimise disturbance to wildlife; no pigeons were captured or
95 handled. Instead, freshly deposited faeces from the environment, enabling non-invasive and
96 ethically responsible sampling were collected. Sampling of feral pigeon (*Columba livia* f.
97 *domestica*) faeces was carried out between September and November 2024 in Brno, Czech
98 Republic. A total of 35 sampling sites (F1 – F35, Table 1) were selected to represent majority
99 of municipal districts of the city; each sampling site corresponded to a different flock.
100 Sampling locations were further stratified into three urban zones: city centre (n = 7 localities),

101 intermediate zone (sub-centre; n = 17), and urban periphery (n = 11). At each site, five pooled
102 samples were obtained, each comprising five freshly deposited pigeon droppings, yielding a
103 total of 175 pooled samples representing 875 individual faecal specimens. Samples were
104 immediately frozen and stored at -70°C until further processing.

2.2. Sample preparation, DNA isolation

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107 Each pooled sample was resuspended in 10 mL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH
108 7.2) and homogenised using an Omni Bead Ruptor Elite (Omni International) at 4 m/s for 30
109 seconds. Subsequently, 500 μL of the homogenate was transferred into a ZR BashingBead™
110 Lysis Tube (Quick-DNA Fecal/Soil Microbe Kit; Zymo Research) and centrifuged at $13,000 \times$
111 $g/1$ min. After removing the supernatant, 750 μl of Bashing Bead buffer (Quick-DNA
112 Fecal/Soil Microbe Kit) and 5 μl of 5×10^5 internal amplification control (IAC) was added
113 (Vojtkovska et al., 2015). DNA extraction was performed in accordance with the
114 manufacturer's protocol. Final elution was carried out using $2 \times 60 \mu\text{L}$ of elution buffer.

2.3. qPCR analysis

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117 Two qPCR triplex assays were developed and used to analyse faecals samples. Both
118 mixes contain 2x EliZyme™ Probe MIX (Elisabeth Pharmacon), 500 nM of each forward and
119 reverse primers, 250 nM of each probe. The final volume was 20 μl , including 5 μl of
120 template DNA. Based on our previous experience with *Mycobacterium* sp. detection
121 (Dziedzinska et al., 2022), the first triplex assay targeted *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *avium*
122 (MAA), *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *hominissuis* (MAH) and IAC. The second multiplex
123 targeted *C. psittaci*, *S. typhimurium* and *T. gallinae* (Table 2). The sequences of primers and
124 probes for MAA, MAH and *C. psittaci* primers and probes were designed in Primer3 software
125 (Untergasser et al., 2012) and verified using IDT Oligo Analyzer tool

126 (eu.idtdna.com/analyzer/Applications/OligoAnalyzer/). Sequences of primers and probes for
127 *S. enterica subsp. enterica* (Malorny et al., 2004) and *T. gallinae* (Sigrist et al., 2022) were
128 retrieved from literature (Table 2).

129 As target DNA sequences were derived from previously published sequences that have
130 been demonstrated to be specific for particular microorganisms (Malorny et al., 2004; Sigrist
131 et al., 2022; Slana et al., 2008; Wolff et al., 2023), an extensive experimental testing of the
132 PCR primers and probes was deemed unnecessary. However, all the primers and probes,
133 whether adopted from previous publications or designed *de novo* in this study, were subjected
134 to *in silico* testing using the BLAST tool against GenBank database to verify exclusivity
135 (target-specific amplification) and inclusivity (coverage of all published sequence of the
136 specific organism by the primers and probes).

137 The qPCR analysis was performed on a LightCycler® 480 Real-Time PCR instrument
138 (Roche Molecular Diagnostics) under the following conditions: initial denaturation step at
139 95°C for 2 minutes, followed by 47 cycles at 95°C for 5 seconds, and at 60°C for 30 seconds.
140 Subsequent analysis was performed using the "Fit point analysis" option of the LightCycler
141 480 software (version 1.5.0.39). Each DNA sample was tested in biological triplicates by each
142 qPCR assay. The mean of the three C_q values was then employed for the subsequent
143 qualitative analysis.

144 The performance and sensitivity of both multiplex qPCR assays were evaluated using
145 a mixture of DNA isolated from the cultured target species and synthetic artificial DNA
146 constructs designed to mimic the target sequence. Isolates of MAA (field isolate AV389) and
147 MAH (field isolate PR21) were propagated on the HEYM medium (Becton Dickinson) at
148 37°C for a period of one week. *S. enterica* isolate (field isolate D49) was cultivated on a XLD
149 Agar (Trios). A single colony from each species was collected, and the DNA was isolated by
150 DNeasy Blood and Tissue kit (Qiagen) using protocols for G⁺ (MAA and MAH) and G⁻

151 (*S. enterica*) bacteria. The isolated DNA was subsequently diluted to 10 ng/μl, which
152 corresponds to approximately 2×10^6 bacterial cells of genome equivalents (GE) in 1 μl. The
153 standards for *C. psittaci* and *T. gallinae* were synthesized *de novo in vitro* (Eurofins
154 Genomics). The synthesized DNA fragments were subsequently diluted to a concentration of
155 5 pM, which corresponds to approximately 3×10^6 DNA fragments in 1 μl. The prepared
156 stock solutions of the isolated DNA and DNA standards were mixed in an equimolar manner.
157 Two DNA mixes were prepared: one for each multiplex. The concentration of each target in
158 the stock mixtures was approximately 10^6 of GE or DNA artificial molecules in 1 μl. These
159 mixtures were serially 10-fold diluted, and dilutions 10^5 , 10^3 , 10^2 , and 10^1 were utilized in the
160 sensitivity testing (Table 3). The dilutions were executed in six technical replicates in each
161 qPCR multiplex. This was done to estimate the repeatability of both assays and to assess the
162 possible interference of the targets' amplification in the multiplex. In all experiments, the
163 dilution 10^5 was utilized as the positive control.

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165 2.4. Statistical analysis

166 All statistical analyses were performed using the R software (2025). First, a
167 hierarchical cluster analysis was conducted based on the distances between the GPS
168 coordinates (in the WGS84 system) of 35 sampling sites. The distance matrix was constructed
169 using geodetic distances, calculated with the *st_distance* function from the *sf* package
170 (Pebesma, 2018; Pebesma and Bivand, 2023). Based on the distance matrix, hierarchical
171 clustering was performed using the average linkage method. Final clusters were identified
172 based on two criteria: (1) a cut-off value for the average linkage distance set at 1,000 or 2,000
173 meters, respectively; and (2) each cluster contained at least five cases. The frequency of
174 pathogen-positive pooled samples was then compared between clusters using the Mann–
175 Whitney U test.

176 The geographic coordinates of sampling sites were visualized on a map using the *ggplot2*
177 package (Wickham, 2016). The administrative boundaries and the positions of watercourses
178 shown on the map were based on spatial data provided by the *RCzechia* package (Lacko,
179 2023).

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181 3. Results and discussion

182 *In silico* testing of exclusivity and inclusivity showed no evidence of potential cross-
183 reactivity. Therefore, all selected oligonucleotides were considered highly specific. The
184 sensitivity of the multiplex assays was evaluated through testing on the serially diluted mixed
185 DNA isolated from the bacteria and artificially synthesized DNA standards. The efficacy of
186 both qPCR multiplex assays was demonstrated through their ability to successfully amplify
187 the lowest concentration of 10^1 of GE or DNA artificial molecules in 1 μ L of the DNA mix,
188 i.e., 5×10^1 per 5 μ L of the qPCR reaction (see Table 3). This sensitivity was deemed
189 adequate for the detection of selected pathogens in this study.

190 Examination of 175 pooled samples representing 875 individual faecal specimens, were
191 successfully analysed using multiplex qPCR assays. *C. psittaci* was detected in 20.6 % of the
192 analysed pools (36/175), representing the highest prevalence among the target pathogens.
193 *T. gallinae* was identified in 9.7 % of samples (17/175) and *S. enterica* subsp. *enterica* in 4 %
194 (7/175). Mycobacteria were infrequently observed: MAH was found in 1.1% (2/175; Fig. 1);
195 MAA was not detected at all.

196 The presence of *C. psittaci* in feral pigeons has been documented across European urban
197 environments, with reported prevalences in faecal samples and cloacal swabs ranging from
198 5 % to 50 % (Geigenfeind et al., 2012; Konicek et al., 2016; Kowalczyk and Wojcik-Fatla,
199 2022; Magnino et al., 2009; Sachse et al., 2012). Seropositivity rates up to 95% have been
200 reported (Magnino et al., 2009). Due to the high seroprevalence observed in pigeons, some

201 authors have suggested that this pathogen may exist in a commensal-like association with its
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2 202 avian hosts (Haag-Wackernagel and Moch, 2004). Transmission to humans typically occurs
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4 203 via inhalation of contaminated dust or bioaerosols containing dried faeces, feather dust, or
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7 204 respiratory and ocular secretions from infected birds (Sachse et al., 2015). Although human
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10 205 psittacosis is generally considered rare, a marked increase in reported cases was observed in
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12 206 several European countries since late 2023 (Izere et al., 2025). Epidemiological
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14 207 investigations revealed that approximately 60 % of the cases were linked to exposure to bird
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17 208 droppings, while 30% of affected individuals reported no known contact with birds. In light of
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19 209 this outbreak, monitoring *C.psittaci* prevalence in wild birds, prompt reporting, and increased
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22 210 public health awareness have been strongly recommended (Izere et al., 2025).

24 211 Feral pigeons in urban environments seem to form relatively isolated populations confined
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26 212 to specific city zones, with limited interaction between flocks. However, hierarchical cluster
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29 213 analysis identified two spatial clusters of sampling sites, using cut-off values of the average
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31 214 linkage distance set to 1,000 meters and 2,000 meters, respectively. Each cluster was
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34 215 sufficiently numerous to meet the inclusion criterion of at least five locations per cluster (Fig.
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36 216 1 and Fig. 2). The red cluster consisted predominantly of *C. psittaci*-positive flocks located in
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39 217 adjacent central districts of the city. In contrast, the blue cluster comprised mostly *C. psittaci*-
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41 218 negative flocks situated in neighbouring areas within the intermediate zone. Statistically
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44 219 significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in the frequency of *C. psittaci*-positive
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46 220 pooled samples across individual sites between the red and blue clusters in both cases,
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49 221 regardless of whether the average distance threshold was set at 1,000 or 2,000 meters. The
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51 222 results suggest a non-random spatial distribution of the infection, which may be attributed
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53 223 either to occasional contact between individual flocks inhabiting neighbouring areas or
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56 224 indirect transmission via environmental contamination (Harkinezhad et al., 2009).
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58 225 Behavioural differences among feral pigeon groups, influenced by varying degrees of
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226 urbanisation within different city zones, has been previously documented. More urbanised
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4 228 stronger resource competition, and altered responses to threats and reproduction (Gonsalves et
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7 229 al., 2025). Such behavioural patterns may partly explain the higher prevalence of *C. psittaci*
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10 230 observed in pigeons from city centre compared to intermediate urban areas, likely resulting
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12 231 from a higher probability of direct contacts among individuals (Fig. 2). In addition, feral
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14 232 pigeons are known to travel between urban and rural areas to forage, covering distances of
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16 233 two to 30 km (Giunchi et al., 2012). Such migratory behaviour could facilitate inter-flock
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18 234 contact at shared feeding sites outside the city. Furthermore, as *C. psittaci* can remain viable
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20 235 in faeces, dust, or bedding material for up to 30 days (Geigenfeind et al., 2012; Harkinezhad
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22 236 et al., 2009), indirect transmission through contaminated environmental surfaces or
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24 237 aggregation points cannot be excluded.
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29 238 In contrast to *C. psittaci*, clustering analysis of *Trichomonas gallinae* did not reveal any
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31 239 statistically significant association between pathogen presence and the spatial proximity of
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33 240 urban areas inhabited by different feral pigeon flocks. Unlike *C. psittaci*, *T. gallinae* does not
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35 241 survive for extended periods outside the host. Transmission occurs primarily via contaminated
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37 242 food or water, but the absence of environmentally resistant cyst stages limits the duration of
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39 243 parasite's infectiousness (Gieger and Furmaga, 2020). *T. gallinae* infections predominantly
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41 244 affect *Columbiformes* and raptors, showing mostly mild symptoms, but with potential to cause
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43 245 severe disease (Amin et al., 2014). Raptors foraging in or near urban environments are
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45 246 particularly at risk, as urbanisation and the loss of natural habitats have led to an increased
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47 247 reliance on feral pigeons as a primary prey source, thereby facilitating transmission of the
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49 248 parasite (Krone et al., 2005). Since 2005, trichomonosis has been recognised as an emerging
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51 249 infectious disease in wild finches in Great Britain (Robinson et al., 2010) with subsequent
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53 250 large-scale outbreaks reported across other parts of Europe (Chavatte et al., 2019). Reported
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251 prevalence in feral pigeons from Poland, Hungary, Romania, and Germany ranges from 8 to
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2 252 40 %; however, these studies were based on relatively small sample sizes (up to 139 samples)
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5 253 (Dovc et al., 2004; Quillfeldt et al., 2018; Tuska-Szalay et al., 2022). In this context, the 175
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7 254 pooled faecal samples representing 875 individual droppings analysed in the present study
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10 255 offer more robust and regionally relevant data on the prevalence of *T. gallinae* in urban feral
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12 256 pigeons in Central Europe. To date, no similar study has been conducted on feral pigeons in
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15 257 the Czech Republic. The only published data from the country refer to *T. gallinae* prevalence
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17 258 in Eurasian sparrowhawks (*Accipiter nisus*), with reported rates of 12.2 % in rural areas and
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19 259 32.9 % in urban zones (Kunca et al., 2015).

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22 260 With a lower prevalence compared to *C. psittaci*, *S. enterica* subsp. *enterica* was detected
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24 261 in 3.9 % of pooled samples. This finding is consistent with previously reported prevalence
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27 262 rates in urban feral pigeon populations, such as in Spain (4.4 %; (Perez-Sancho et al., 2020)
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29 263 Ljubljana, Slovenia (5.7 %; (Dovc et al., 2004) and Poland (5.5 %; (Kaczorek-Lukowska et
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31 264 al., 2021). Infected pigeons are typically asymptomatic and appear clinically healthy
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34 265 (Kaczorek-Lukowska et al., 2021), which was also the case in our study. Evidence of
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36 266 mycobacteria was either absent (MAA) or negligible (MAH; 1.1 %). Published reports of
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39 267 MAA prevalence in pigeons primarily focus on domesticated flocks, often in late stages of
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41 268 disease progression (Kriz et al., 2011). To date, the only documented presence of avian
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44 269 tuberculosis in free-ranging pigeons in the Czech Republic was published in 1994, reporting a
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46 270 prevalence of 1 % (Hejlíček and Tremel, 1994). More recent study from the Czech Republic
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49 271 did not reveal any mycobacteria in wild birds (Koníček et al., 2016). Among other wild bird
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51 272 species, such as raptors and gulls, prevalence rate of MAA ranging between 0.7 and 2.4 %
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53
54 273 have been reported (Millán et al., 2010; Smit et al., 1987). Therefore, our study contributes
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56 274 updated data on the occurrence of MAA in feral urban pigeons in Brno, a major city in
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58 275 Central Europe, providing new epidemiological insights into the occurrence of avian
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276 tuberculosis in free-ranging urban bird populations. The overall low prevalence of both
1
2 277 *Mycobacterium* spp. and *Salmonella* spp. suggests that feral pigeons play a limited role in the
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5 278 transmission of these pathogens within the urban environment.
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7 279 Urban environments offer favourable conditions for feral pigeons due to increased
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10 280 availability of food resources, shelter, nesting opportunities, and a relative absence of natural
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12 281 predators (Gonsalves et al., 2025). Common management strategies for controlling pigeon
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14 282 populations include culling, reproductive suppression through egg removal or replacement
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17 283 with dummy eggs, and reduction of the habitat's carrying capacity. As the first two approaches
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19 284 have shown limited long-term efficacy, the most effective and publicly acceptable method
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21
22 285 appears to be the restriction of nesting and roosting opportunities, e.g. the installation of
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24 286 physical barriers and deterrent systems to prevent access to suitable nesting sites (Giunchi et
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26
27 287 al., 2012; Magnino et al., 2009). These preventive measures do not only reduce costs
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29 288 associated with faecal contamination and building damage but also help to minimise the risk
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32 289 of zoonotic pathogen transmission from feral pigeons to humans. To maintain effectiveness,
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34 290 population control efforts should be implemented continuously and throughout the year
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36 291 (Giunchi et al., 2012). Although the general public health risk posed by feral pigeons is
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39 292 considered low, personal protective clothes and mask are necessary for risk group of people,
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41 293 mainly workers handling with dead pigeons or their droppings. Vulnerable populations,
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44 294 including children and immunocompromised individuals, should be advised to avoid contact
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46 295 with sick or dead pigeons (Magnino et al., 2009).
47

48 296 The study has potential limitations. All samples were collected during the autumn months
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51 297 (September to November), which may potentially influence the observed pathogen
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53 298 prevalence. Seasonal factors - such as temperature, humidity, or pigeon behaviour - may affect
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56 299 both pathogen persistence and host susceptibility. To mitigate these effects, freshly deposited
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58 300 faeces were collected and molecular assays that do not rely on pathogen viability, were
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301 applied. While molecular detection of pathogen DNA in faeces provides valuable
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2 302 epidemiological insight, it does not necessarily reflect the clinical status or active infection in
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4 303 individual birds. Nonetheless, faecal screening is a practical and widely accepted approach for
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7 304 monitoring pathogen circulation in urban wildlife populations.
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12 306 **4. Conclusions**

14 307 This study confirms that feral pigeons in Brno, the city in central Europe with
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16 308 approximately 400 thousand inhabitants, harbour zoonotic pathogens of public health
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18 309 concern, particularly *C. psittaci*. The observed spatial clustering of *C. psittaci* flocks is
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21 310 statistically significant and suggests non-random distribution of infection, mainly in dense
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24 311 urban areas. While *T. gallinae*, *S. enterica* and *M. avium* complex were detected at lower
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26 312 frequencies, their presence underscores the importance of ongoing surveillance. The data
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28
29 313 support the need for preventive measures to reduce human exposure. To our knowledge, this
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31 314 is the first comprehensive screening of these pathogens in urban pigeons in the Czech
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34 315 Republic, providing important baseline data for regional public health authorities and
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36 316 contributing to the broader understanding of zoonotic risks in Central European cities.
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38 317

41 318 **Acknowledgement**

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45 320 SS06020195.
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51 322 **Ethics Statement**

53 323 An ethics statement is not applicable as this study was not classified as a human or
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55 324 animal experiment. Faecal samples examined in this study were field-collected from non-
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58 325 protected areas.
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2 **327 Data Availability Statement**
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5 **328** The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding
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7 **329** author upon reasonable request.
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14 **332** References
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459 Table 1. Number of qPCR positive results (pools) for feral pigeon faecal sampling sites.

Site	MAH	CHP	SE	TG	category	Lat	Lon
F1	0	4	0	2	3	49.19819	16.66642
F2	0	1	0	2	2	49.19026	16.59338
F3	0	1	0	0	1	49.18998	16.61397
F4	0	0	0	0	3	49.20515	16.68017
F5	0	0	0	0	3	49.20389	16.67065
F6	0	1	0	1	1	49.19352	16.60668
F7	0	1	0	1	2	49.2103	16.61665
F8	0	1	0	0	2	49.20991	16.61617
F9	0	1	0	0	2	49.20981	16.6155
F10	0	1	0	0	1	49.1914	16.61235
F11	0	1	1	1	2	49.18459	16.61579
F12	0	1	0	0	2	49.19295	16.62161
F13	1	0	0	1	2	49.20495	16.59415
F14	0	2	0	1	3	49.17551	16.55393
F15	0	0	0	0	2	49.20261	16.63973
F16	0	0	0	1	1	49.19705	16.6162
F17	0	3	0	1	3	49.20529	16.66404
F18	0	2	1	0	2	49.18823	16.59432
F19	0	1	0	0	3	49.17084	16.55929
F20	0	4	0	0	3	49.17637	16.57376
F21	1	4	0	1	1	49.19159	16.60965
F22	0	2	0	0	1	49.1924	16.60761
F23	0	1	0	0	3	49.16989	16.58319
F24	0	1	0	0	2	49.19	16.59105
F25	0	0	0	1	3	49.18947	16.53066
F26	0	1	0	1	3	49.21677	16.5055
F27	0	1	0	2	3	49.21685	16.53049
F28	0	0	1	1	2	49.20585	16.60478
F29	0	0	0	0	2	49.20378	16.60322
F30	0	0	3	0	1	49.1901	16.61355
F31	0	1	0	0	2	49.20469	16.60131
F32	0	0	0	0	2	49.2024	16.59609
F33	0	0	0	0	2	49.20321	16.59573
F34	0	0	1	0	2	49.21113	16.5927
F35	0	0	0	0	2	49.2119	16.58413

460 Category - Sampling locations covered city centre (category 1), intermediate zone (sub-
461 centre; category 2), and urban periphery (category 3).

462 CHP – *Chlamydia psittaci*; Lat – Latitude; Lon – longitude; MAH – *Mycobacterium avium*
463 subsp. *hominissuis*; SE – *Salmonella enterica*; TG – *Trichomonas gallinae*

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465 Table 2. Sequences of primers and probes used in this study.

Species	Name	Sequence 5' – 3'	Target gene sequence	Length	Source
<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> <i>subsp. avium</i>	IS901F	CCGTTGATCCTGGTATCCGC	IS901	114	This study
	IS901R	CGTGTTCGATGTTGTTGGGC			
	IS901P	FAM-CGGTCGGCAAAAAGAGCTGG-BHQ1			
<i>Mycobacterium avium</i> <i>subsp. hominissuis</i> [†]	IS1245F	GTGGAGTGGTGTAAAGAGCGG	IS1245	96	This study
	IS1245R	AAAGTGCCGAAACCATTGCC			
	IS1245P	HEX-AGCCACTATGCCGTGAGAGC-BHQ1			
IAC	IAC F	AGAGGACCGGGATATTCGAC	Artificial	141	Vojkowska et al., 2015
	IAC R	AGGTAGTCCGAGGAAAACTCTAAAC			
	IAC P	Cy5-AGGCTCTTCTATGTTCTGACCTTGTGGA- BHQ2			
<i>Chlamydia psittaci</i>	CHPF1	AGTTGGCAGTGTCTTTATGGG	Autotransporter beta- domain protein	87	This study
	CHPR1	AGTTTACATTTGAAGGTGGTGCG			
	CHPP1	FAM-ACAAGAAGCACTCAACCTGAAATTC- BHQ1			
<i>Salmonella enterica</i> <i>subsp. enterica</i>	ttrF	CTCACCAGGAGATTACAACATGG	ttrRSBCA locus	95	Malorny et al., 2004
	ttrR	AGCTCAGACCAAAAAGTGACCATC			
	ttrP	HEX-CACCGACGGCGAGACCGACTTT-BHQ1			
<i>Trichomonas gallinae</i>	TriTet4(+)	CCGTGATGCCCTTAGATGC	18S rDNA	143	Sigrist et al., 2022
	TriTet4(-)	TCCTGGTTCATGACGCTGAT			
	Trich_Cy5	Cy5-CGCGGCCTCTCGGCTTGCA-BHQ2			

466 † IS1245 is present in the MAA genome as well, but only in a single copy. Therefore, the results interpretation was IS901+ve/IS1245+ve means
467 MAA is present; IS901-ve/IS1245+ve means MAH is present. Possible mixed infection would be indistinguishable.

468

469 Table 3. Sensitivity of multiplex qPCR assays.

qPCR	Species	Amount of DNA (GE) in 1 μ l			
		10 ⁵	10 ³	10 ²	10 ¹
Multiplex 1	MAA	6/6	6/6	6/6	6/6
	MAH	6/6	6/6	6/6	6/6
Multiplex 2	<i>C. psittaci</i>	6/6	6/6	6/6	6/6
	<i>S. enterica</i>	6/6	6/6	6/6	6/6
	<i>T. gallinae</i>	6/6	6/6	6/6	6/6

470 The numbers in the table represent a signal ratio, which is number of positive results/no of
 471 replicates.

472 MAA - *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *avium*, MAH - *Mycobacterium avium* subsp.
 473 *hominissuis*

474 Figure legend

475

476 Figure 1. Hierarchical clustering of pigeon flocks based on spatial distance

477

478 Dendrogram showing hierarchical clustering of 35 pooled pigeon faecal sampling sites (F1–
 479 F35) in the city of Brno, based on average linkage distances. Additional columns show
 480 detection of *C. psittaci* (CHP, highlighted with a yellow rectangle), *Mycobacterium avium*
 481 subsp. *hominissuis* (MAH), *Salmonella enterica* (SE), and *Trichomonas gallinae* (TG) at each
 482 site. Vertical dashed lines indicate clustering thresholds at 1,000 m and 2,000 m. Identified
 483 clusters are color-coded: red cluster contains mostly CHP-positive flocks (sites), blue cluster
 484 mostly CHP-negative flocks (sites). Dark and light red/blue corresponding to 1,000 m and
 485 2,000 m clustering threshold, respectively.

486

487

488 Figure 2. Geographic distribution of pigeon faecal sampling sites within Brno

490
491 Map of Brno showing the locations of 35 pooled pigeon faecal sampling sites (F1–F35),
492 marked as squares. Red and blue squares indicate the sites included in red and blue cluster,
493 respectively, as shown in Fig. 1, based on hierarchical clustering with a clustering threshold
494 set at 2,000 m. Black squares indicate remaining sampling sites, which were not classified
495 into any cluster at 2,000 m threshold. The Brno Reservoir and the Svatka and Svitava rivers
496 are shown in light blue. The central municipal district, Brno-střed, is highlighted in dark grey.

497

Fig 1

[Click here to access/download;Figure \(300 dpi and editable format\);Fig 1.png](#)

Fig 2

[Click here to access/download;Figure \(300 dpi and editable format\);Fig 2.png](#)

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Feral pigeons as reservoirs of zoonotic pathogens in the urban environment: Spatial clustering and molecular evidence

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